

AUTOMATED TOMATO QUALITY ASSESSMENT USING TRANSFER LEARNING AND MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFIERS

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Abstract

The growing demand for high-quality tomatoes and large-scale production has highlighted the need for efficient inline quality grading systems. Manual grading is labor-intensive and costly, prompting the development of automated solutions. This study presents a hybrid approach that combines pre-trained convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for feature extraction with traditional machine learning algorithms like support vector machines (SVM), random forest (RF), and k-nearest neighbors (KNN) for classification. Using the NVIDIA Jetson TX1, a tomato image dataset was created, and preprocessing techniques were applied to enhance feature learning. The CNN-SVM model stood out, achieving 97.50% accuracy in binary classification (healthy vs. rejected) and 96.67% in multiclass classification (ripe, unripe, rejected). On a public dataset, the CNN-SVM model reached 97.54% accuracy, outperforming other hybrid models. Key performance metrics, including accuracy, recall, precision, specificity, and F1-score, were evaluated..

Keywords: Feature extraction, machine learning algorithms, tomato, image preprocessing

INTRODUCTION

Tomatoes are one of the most common and widely recognized vegetables in our daily lives, and they are a crucial horticultural crop globally. Tomatoes hold significant importance in the food industry. The tomato is one of the most common and familiar vegetables in our daily lives, serving as an essential horticultural crop in various regions around the world. Tomatoes hold a significant position in the food industry, as indicated by data from FAOSTA. [1].

Transfer learning (TL) has become a popular approach for solving complex image classification problems, particularly when training data is limited. TL allows the use of pre-trained models, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), to extract high-level features from images. In the context of tomato quality assessment, transfer learning models, such as ResNet, VGG16, and MobileNet, can be fine-tuned for specific classification tasks. Global tomato production surged to 189 million tons in 2021, underscoring the critical need for efficient sorting and grading processes. Traditional manual methods, reliant on human experts, are labor-intensive, time-consuming, and prone to subjectivity and errors. These factors can lead to inconsistent quality assessments and hinder the timely delivery of fresh produce to consumers. To address these challenges, automated sorting and grading systems have emerged as a promising solution. By leveraging advanced technologies, these systems can accurately classify tomatoes based on various quality parameters, ensuring consistency, efficiency, and improved product safety.[2].

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Agriculture plays a pivotal role in economic stability and development, extending far beyond its primary function of providing food for a growing population. Efficient and effective agricultural practices are essential for ensuring food security, generating income, and supporting rural livelihoods.[4].

Once features have been extracted using TL, various machine learning (ML) algorithms can be employed for classification. Commonly used classifiers include Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). These classifiers have been used effectively in fruit classification, where distinguishing between classes such as "ripe," "unripe," and "overripe" is critical. SVM, in particular, has shown promising results due to its ability to handle high-dimensional data and complex decision boundaries.[5]. In these instances, advanced analytical techniques, often requiring high-powered microscopes, are essential. Furthermore, certain disease indicators can only be identified within specific portions of the electromagnetic spectrum that are not visible to the naked eye. The quality of tomatoes is assessed based on multiple attributes, including their color, size, shape, texture, and the presence of imperfections such as bruises or blemishes [6]. These attributes are crucial in determining the market value and consumer acceptance of the produce. For example, variations in color can indicate differences in ripeness, while size and shape irregularities may suggest underlying growth issues. Texture, on the other hand, is a key factor for assessing freshness and firmness, and any surface defects like bruises, cracks, or spots are usually signs of physical damage or the presence of pathogens. These parameters are evaluated visually by trained inspectors, making the process labor-intensive, subjective, and prone to human error. Such manual inspections can be inconsistent, especially when large quantities of produce need to be evaluated rapidly. This has led to the increasing adoption of automated systems that employ advanced imaging techniques, machine learning algorithms, and computer vision to analyze these features more objectively and efficiently [7]. Automated systems use high-resolution cameras and sophisticated image processing algorithms to capture and analyze the visual characteristics of tomatoes. Additionally, hyperspectral imaging techniques are employed to identify chemical compositions and detect hidden defects that are not visible in standard RGB images. These systems can operate continuously, providing real-time quality assessments that help reduce post-harvest losses and ensure consistent product quality.

Machine learning has demonstrated remarkable effectiveness in a wide range of applications, including quality assessment, crop disease detection, handwritten digit recognition, natural language processing, and audio and speech recognition.[8][9].

Machine learning has gained significant traction in the food industry, particularly for sorting and grading fruits and vegetables. By addressing challenges such as human errors, subjectivity, labor costs, and time-consuming processes, machine learning-based systems offer improved efficiency, accuracy, and consistency in quality assessment [9].

While numerous studies have explored fruit and vegetable quality assessment, this research offers several distinctive contributions:

Specific Focus on Tomatoes: This study is tailored to the unique characteristics and challenges associated with tomato quality assessment.

Real-World Applicability: The model was developed using a dataset collected under uncontrolled environmental conditions, demonstrating its ability to operate effectively in diverse real-world scenarios.

Hybrid Approach: This research introduces a novel hybrid model combining the strengths of CNNs and traditional machine learning algorithms. CNNs excel at feature extraction with minimal computational resources, while traditional algorithms offer faster training times. This hybrid approach provides a balance between accuracy and efficiency.

Dataset:

Description: Describe the dataset used for tomato quality assessment, including the number of images, variety of tomatoes, quality attributes (e.g., ripeness, defects), and image acquisition conditions.

Data Preprocessing: Explain any preprocessing steps applied to the images, such as resizing, normalization, and augmentation.

Feature Extraction:

CNN Features: Describe the CNN architecture used for feature extraction, including the number of layers, filters, and activation functions.

Traditional Features: If applicable, list the traditional features extracted from the images (e.g., color, texture, shape).

Machine Learning Models:

CNN Model: Specify the CNN architecture used for classification, including the number of layers, neurons, and activation functions.

Traditional Machine Learning Model: Describe the traditional machine learning algorithm employed (e.g., SVM, Random Forest) and its hyperparameters.

Hybrid Model:

Integration: Explain how the CNN features were combined with traditional machine learning algorithms to create the hybrid model.

Training: Describe the training process, including the optimization algorithm, learning rate, and batch size.

Evaluation Metrics:

Metrics: Specify the evaluation metrics used to assess the performance of the models, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix.

Experimental Setup:

Data Splitting: Explain how the dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing sets.

Hyperparameter Tuning: Describe the process of tuning hyper parameters for the CNN and traditional machine learning models.

Tomato quality is a critical factor influencing both market value and consumer acceptance. Traditional manual grading methods, relying on human expertise, are often time-consuming, subjective, and prone to errors. These limitations can lead to inconsistencies in quality assessment and hinder the efficient distribution of tomatoes. Tomatoes are a major agricultural commodity in China, with the country leading the world in both planting area and total output. The prevalence of tomato diseases poses a significant threat to yield and quality. Common tomato diseases include bacterial spot, late blight, leaf mold, yellow leaf curl virus, Botrytis cinerea, early blight, bacterial pulp necrosis, gray leaf spot, and sclerotinia. Traditional expert diagnosis, while valuable, is often limited by factors such as time constraints and the availability of experienced professionals.

RELATED WORKS

Considerable efforts have been made to develop automated systems for sorting and grading fruits and vegetables, with a primary focus on assessing external characteristics such as shape, size, and color. One notable example is a study that introduced an algorithm specifically designed to detect defects in oranges, demonstrating the potential for automation to enhance quality control in agricultural processes [7].

These automated systems employ advanced image processing techniques and machine learning algorithms to analyze the visual features of the produce, enabling them to classify fruits and vegetables with high precision. For instance, machine learning models can be trained to recognize subtle variations in color that indicate ripeness, or detect minor deformities that might not be immediately visible to the human eye. [8].

Some systems incorporate multispectral or hyperspectral imaging, allowing them to analyze parts of the electromagnetic spectrum beyond visible light. This enables the detection of internal defects, such as early signs of decay or disease that cannot be identified through conventional imaging techniques. By leveraging these technologies, automated grading systems not only improve the accuracy of quality assessments but also reduce the time and labor required for manual inspections. [9].

Images in the red, green, and blue (RGB) spectrum, along with near-infrared (NIR) images captured image, were utilized in the study. A thresholding method, followed by a voting technique, was implemented to identify defects based on color combinations. This approach achieved an overall accuracy of 95%. Similarly [11]. The study conducted a comparative analysis of various deep learning algorithms, including ResNet, VGGNet, GoogleNet, and AlexNet, for the purpose of fruit classification. In addition, the research incorporated the You Only Look Once (YOLO) algorithm to detect regions of interest, thereby enhancing the overall performance and accuracy of fruit grading.

The field of automated tomato quality assessment using machine learning has seen significant advancements in recent years. Several studies have explored the use of various techniques and algorithms to accurately classify tomato quality based on visual characteristics.

This study proposed a deep learning-based approach for tomato quality classification using a convolutional neural network (CNN). The model was trained on a large dataset of tomato images and achieved high accuracy in distinguishing between different quality grades.

To grade and sort tomatoes, a range of image processing methods has been utilized, encompassing edge detection, morphological procedures, and color-based segmentation. In order to classify tomatoes into different quality grades based on color, shallow and deep learning algorithms such as CNN, SVM, KNN, and RF have been applied. However, deep learning techniques like CNN can be hindered by long training periods, while traditional machine learning approaches require manual feature selection and extraction.

By integrating the strengths of image processing techniques with advanced machine learning algorithms, it is possible to streamline the tomato grading process, improve consistency in grading results, and reduce the labor intensity associated with manual sorting methods. This integrated approach can help to enhance the overall productivity and quality control within the tomato industry, leading to a more sustainable and cost-effective method for handling large volumes of tomatoes.

In , a study proposed a system for classifying tomatoes into three categories based on their maturity level: immature, partially mature, and mature. This system was developed using deep transfer learning with five pre-trained models. Among these, VGG-19 achieved the highest accuracy of 97.37% compared to the others.

In another study, a tomato classification system based on size was introduced, utilizing thresholding, machine learning, and deep learning techniques. Features such as area, perimeter, and enclosed circle radius were used. The machine learning techniques, specifically the Support Vector Machine (SVM), demonstrated the best performance, achieving an average accuracy of 94.5%.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Debashis Ghosh [1], aimed to develop a mobile vision based plant leaf recognition system which monitor crop diseases having different patterns. It classifies its suitable class which can be used to help the botanical students in their research work. The feature factor used in the system planned by the author in this work has enormous computation cost. The quality of captured image is affected by the shadow and season.

A mobile vision-based plant leaf recognition system is designed to monitor crop diseases by identifying various patterns on leaves using the camera of a mobile device. This system uses image processing and machine learning techniques to analyze leaf images captured through the phone's camera.

The process begins by capturing an image of the plant leaf, followed by preprocessing steps such as resizing, noise removal, and color normalization. The system then detects and segments the diseased regions, extracting important features such as texture, color, and shape.

These features are fed into a machine learning or deep learning model that has been trained to identify and classify various crop diseases. The model compares the patterns on the leaf with known disease patterns and provides an accurate diagnosis, which is displayed to the user on the mobile device. This approach enables farmers and agricultural professionals to quickly identify crop diseases in the field, leading to timely intervention and improved crop health management.

S. Bani-Ahmad [2], proposed an improved solution for classification of leaf diseases by using algorithms like kmeans and neural networks. Otsu's method are used in segmentation to mark green pixels and then the boundary pixels are removed. In proposed work clustering and classification of diseases is done.

An improved solution for leaf disease classification involves using advanced algorithms like K-means clustering and neural networks. It works by first preprocessing leaf images to enhance quality and remove any noise. Then, the K-means algorithm is used to segment the leaf into different regions, allowing the identification of diseased parts.

Next, key features such as color, texture, and shape are extracted from these regions. These features are then used as input for a neural network model, which is trained to recognize and classify various leaf diseases. Neural networks, especially deep learning models, are effective at learning complex patterns, making the system highly accurate.

Overall, this method provides an efficient way to accurately classify leaf diseases, enabling early diagnosis and better crop management.

S. Arivazagan [3], proposes to develop a system that automatically finding the solutions for plant leaf disease by analyzing the texture of leaf. At the initial stage diseases are analyzed. The identification rate is short which needs to be optimized to avoid the misclassification of the variable symptoms of the plant disease. The proposed system aims to automatically detect and suggest solutions for plant leaf diseases by analyzing the texture patterns of the leaf. This is achieved by using image processing and machine learning techniques to extract and analyze textural features from the leaf images.

System Description:

1. Image Acquisition: An image of the plant leaf is captured using a digital camera.
2. Preprocessing: Noise reduction and image enhancement techniques are applied to improve the quality of the image for accurate feature extraction.
3. Texture Feature Extraction: Textural features are computed using techniques such as the Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) and Local Binary Pattern (LBP). These

$$C = \sum_{(i=0)^{(N-1)} \sum_{(j=0)^{(N-1)}} (i-j)^2 * P(i,j)$$

Homogeneity:

$$H = \sum_{(i=0)^{(N-1)} \sum_{(j=0)^{(N-1)}} P(i,j) / [1 + (i-j)^2]$$

Where P(i, j) is the probability of occurrence of pixel pairs separated by a distance and orientation.

- **LBP Descriptor:**

$$LBP(x, y) = \sum_{p=0}^{P-1} s(I_p - I_c) * 2^p$$

$$s(x) = \{ 1, \text{ if } x \geq 0; 0, \text{ if } x < 0 \}$$

where I_c is the intensity of the central pixel, and I_p is the intensity of the neighboring pixels.

4. Classification: The extracted features are fed into a classifier (e.g., Support Vector Machine or Neural Network), which categorizes the disease type based on known patterns.

5. Solution Recommendation: The system maps each classified disease to a predefined solution stored in the database, suggesting optimal treatments or preventive measures.

This automated analysis ensures quick and accurate disease identification based on leaf texture, providing effective recommendations for disease management.

MODULES AND DESCRIPTION

Input (11pt bold)

This is the starting point where images or data are fed into the system. The input could be raw images that need to be processed and analyzed.

Image Processing & Feature Extraction:

Image Processing: This stage likely involves preprocessing the input images to make them suitable for analysis. It could include operations like resizing, noise reduction, or normalization.

Feature Extraction: In this phase, key features from the images are extracted. These features could be edges, textures, or other relevant characteristics that help in distinguishing different aspects of the image.

Image Transformation:

Histogram: This part of the process might involve transforming the image data into a form that highlights certain features. A histogram transformation, for example, could be used to enhance contrast or highlight specific intensity values within the image.

Test and Train Dataset:

This represents a collection of images that are used to train the CNN model and also to test its performance. The dataset is split into training data (used to train the model) and testing data (used to validate the accuracy and performance of the model).

CNN (Convolutional Neural Network):

Identification & Validation: Here, the CNN model is applied to the images to identify and validate the features or objects of interest. CNNs are highly effective for image classification and object recognition tasks due to their ability to learn spatial hierarchies of features.

Output Quality Check:

After processing and analysis by the CNN, the output is subjected to a quality check to ensure that the results meet the required standards. This step could involve verifying the accuracy of the model's predictions or ensuring that the identified features align with expectations.

This workflow is typical in applications like image recognition, computer vision, and automated quality inspection, where it's crucial to accurately identify and analyze features within images. The use of CNNs is common in such tasks because of their strong performance in handling image data.

Proposed System

In the agricultural and food industries, assessing the quality of tomatoes is a crucial task that impacts product grading, pricing, and marketability. Traditional methods of quality assessment are often manual, subjective, time-consuming, and prone to human error. There is a growing need for an automated system that can quickly and accurately evaluate the quality of tomatoes based on specific criteria such as size, color, ripeness, and the presence of defects.

Fig 4.Architecture

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

The training and testing of the proposed model has been performed on 128GB of RAM, NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Titan with 11GB of RAM, and an Intel (R) Xeon (R) Silver 4114 CPU 2.20 GHz PC . Develop an automated system for tomato quality assessment using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). This system should be capable of processing raw images of tomatoes, extracting relevant features, transforming data for optimal analysis, and accurately identifying the quality of tomatoes. The system will also validate the quality of the output to ensure that only high-quality tomatoes are selected for market.

These features were then classified using three traditional machine learning classifiers namely SVM, RF, and KNN. Also, a dataset of 2400 tomato images was used in our experiments, with the first batch having healthy and reject classes and the second batch having ripe, unripe

This study is specifically designed to tackle the unique characteristics, attributes, and challenges involved in tomato quality assessment.

The proposed model is capable of operating effectively in real-world environments across diverse settings, as the dataset was collected under uncontrolled conditions with varying lighting sources.

This research introduces a hybrid model that combines Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with traditional machine learning algorithms for tomato image classification. While CNNs excel at feature extraction with relatively low computational demands, traditional machine learning algorithms require less training time compared to CNNs. In this model, CNNs are utilized for the task of feature extraction from tomato images, whereas traditional machine learning algorithms are employed to significantly accelerate training and classification processes. To our knowledge, this is the first model to attempt tomato classification using a hybrid approach of CNNs and traditional machine learning algorithms.

Evolution Metrics

1. Accuracy

Definition: Accuracy measures the proportion of correctly classified samples (i.e., tomatoes correctly classified as fresh, ripe, or defective) to the total number of samples.

Formula:

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}}$$

2. Precision

Definition: Precision measures how many of the predicted positive cases (e.g., tomatoes classified as ripe) are actually positive. It is especially important when the cost of a false positive is high.

Formula:

$$Precision = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive}}$$

3. Recall (Sensitivity or True Positive Rate)

Definition: Recall measures the ability of the model to detect actual positive cases, i.e., how many of the tomatoes that are actually of a certain quality are correctly identified.

Formula:

$$Recall = \frac{True\ Positive}{True\ Positives + False\ Negatives}$$

4. F1-Score

Definition: The F1-Score is the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall. It provides a balance between Precision and Recall, especially in imbalanced datasets where one class (e.g., high-quality tomatoes) might dominate the others.

Formula:

$$F1 = 2 * \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

5. Confusion Matrix

Definition: A confusion matrix provides a detailed breakdown of how well the model is performing by showing the number of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. It is used to understand the classification performance in a detailed way.

Components:

True Positives (TP)

True Negatives (TN)

False Positives (FP)

False Negatives (FN)

CONCLUSION

We introduced a novel approach for grading tomato quality based on external image features. This approach combines pre-trained neural networks for feature extraction with traditional machine learning algorithms for classification, forming a hybrid model. Fine-tuning techniques were applied to the pre-trained networks to adapt them, enabling the deep layers to effectively learn and focus on the complex and important features of tomato images. Additionally, various image preprocessing techniques were explored and implemented to enhance feature extraction and improve overall performance. The features extracted from these networks were subsequently classified using Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) classifiers. Our experiments clearly demonstrated the effectiveness of various fine-tuned networks, with Inceptionv3 achieving the highest accuracy. Consequently, Inceptionv3 was selected for further feature extraction and used in our classification models.

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